

EDGE Digital Manufacturing:

Making the case for digital investment
through data and AI

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CASE STUDY

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Small and medium-sized manufacturers are increasingly embracing digital transformation – but many lack the tools and guidance needed to assess their progress. Understanding how digital readiness links to business performance is especially important for smaller companies, which must make the case for investment with limited time and resource.

Investment in the right digital technologies could be critical for SMEs' success: AI adoption has the potential to transform the manufacturing industry by delivering new efficiencies, optimising production processes, and enabling data-driven decision-making at every level of the business.

[EDGE Digital Manufacturing](#) is a consultancy that helps SMEs develop digital strategies and roadmaps, and create the right conditions for successful adoption. Co-founded in 2018 by leadership development and digital transformation specialists Ravi Gidoomal and Dr Steven Barr, EDGE has worked with clients across the UK to support innovation, upskilling and technology adoption. The company's tools, workshops and methodologies are grounded in real-world insight, including contributions to the national Digital Readiness Level tool and British Standards on digital transformation.

“This has been a genuinely collaborative and energising experience. The ISA offer gave us access to high-level expertise through Kit that we would have struggled to find or afford otherwise. It has helped us to move faster, ask better questions, and build confidence in applying AI within our business. The insights and connections we gained continue to shape our direction.”

Ravi Gidoomal,
co-founder, EDGE Digital Manufacturing

Credit: EDGE Digital Manufacturing

In 2024, EDGE took part in Innovate UK's BridgeAI Independent Scientific Advisor (ISA) offer. This connected the team with Professor Kit Windows-Yule, a data science expert from the University of Birmingham and The Alan Turing Institute. The collaboration focused on using AI and machine learning techniques to analyse EDGE's own digital readiness dataset – drawn from over 1,000 manufacturing leaders – and to help SMEs see how improved digital readiness can drive better business performance.

The project aimed to identify patterns in strategic data collected from SME leaders, using advanced techniques such as symbolic regression and random forest regression.

Kit became a core part of the project team, offering weekly guidance, mentoring junior staff, and sharing tools, models and best practice from his academic and industry networks. His input contributed significantly to the final analysis, which was published as part of [EDGE's Smart Manufacturing Data Hub-funded project](#). The report revealed a clear link between leadership attitudes and digital performance, highlighting both the potential for data and AI-driven transformation in UK manufacturing and the urgent need for better tools to support strategic decision-making.

Credit: EDGE Digital Manufacturing

“The biggest challenge in this project was the size of the dataset,” says Kit. “We had to rule out several AI techniques that just don’t work well with small or unbalanced data. In the end, we focused on symbolic regression – a machine learning technique that automatically generates equations to describe relationships in data.” This approach allowed EDGE to reduce its 40-question digital readiness survey down to just six key items, enabling simpler and more effective collection of insights from manufacturing companies. “It clears the runway for future projects using deeper AI techniques,” adds Kit.

The ISA collaboration has also led to wider engagement and opportunity with BridgeAI partners: EDGE has shared its work at The Turing’s flagship AI UK conference and taken part in its Mini Data Study Groups, in which early-career research talent helps organisations solve real-world business challenges. This has helped sharpen the company’s understanding of AI’s potential – and boosted its confidence to hire more AI-focused staff. “We’ve taken on five interns this summer, including two focused on AI and technology,” says Ravi. “The ISA offer played a large part in that decision.”

EDGE is now exploring new frontiers, including the human aspects of technology and how digital adoption links to wellbeing and mental health in the workplace.

Ravi Gidoomal, co-founder, EDGE Digital Manufacturing

About Innovate UK BridgeAI

Innovate UK BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. We bridge the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency and data privacy, we aim to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

BridgeAI is an Innovate UK funded programme, delivered by a consortium including Innovate UK, Digital Catapult, The Alan Turing Institute, STFC Hartree and BSI.

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This work is led by **Dr Vera Matser**, Head of Strategic Capabilities and Principal Investigator for BridgeAI at The Alan Turing Institute.

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